

Studies on N-Substituted Salicylhydroxamic Acid as Metal-Complexing Ligand : Part III. Iron (III) Complexes

Nripendra Nath Ghosh and Aruna Bhattacharyya

N-Phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid (RH_2) forms coloured complexes with Fe(III). The compositions of the complexes were determined by Job's method of continued variation and also by Slope-ratio method in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. The violet coloured complex studied at lower pH 0.40 had the composition $\text{Fe} : \text{RH}_2 = 1 : 1$ and orange-red coloured complex had the ratio $\text{Fe} : \text{RH}_2 = 1 : 2$ formed at pH 3.5. At higher pH a solid product was isolated having the composition $\text{Fe} : \text{RH}_2 = 1 : 3$.

N-Phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid (RH_2) forms two different coloured complexes with Fe (III) in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol at different pH values. Job's method of continued variation¹ and the Slope-ratio method² were applied for determining the composition of the complexes. The maximum values found in equimolecular solution corresponds to a composition $\text{Fe} : \text{RH}_2 = 1 : 1$ at $\text{pH} \approx 0.40$ and $\text{Fe} : \text{RH}_2 = 1 : 2$ at $\text{pH} \approx 3.5$. At higher pH, RH_2 gave 1 : 3 complex³ with Fe(III) which is chocolate-red in colour and sparingly soluble in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. So its formation could not be studied in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. 1 : 1 complex gives violet colour and 1 : 2 orange-red colour in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. The same results were obtained also by the Slope-ratio method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Optical densities of the solutions were measured both with a spectrophotometer and Spekker Absorptiometer. Results from the absorptiometer readings tallied with the results from spectrophotometer readings. Results are stated graphically. At higher pH, 1 : 3 compound was precipitated (Found Fe=7.44% ; $\text{Fe}(\text{RH})_3$ requires Fe-7.55%).

A : *Job's method* :—Equimolecular solutions of Ferric Chloride and the reagent (RH_2) were prepared in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. pHs of the mixtures were adjusted carefully with standard hydrochloric acid and/or sodium acetate solution. Final volume was made upto 25ml in each case. The optical densities were measured against water and the differences of the values observed and the calculated values if there be no such complex formation, were plotted as a function of the composition of the mixture.

1. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, (10), 9, 113.
2. A. E. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
3. N. N. Ghosh and A. Bhattacharyya, *This Journal*, 1964, 41, 311.

From Fig-1 it is evident that at $pH \approx 0.40$ the maximum value at $540 m\mu$ and $480 m\mu$, and with the yellowish green filter at two different but equimolecular solutions

Curve I $pH \approx 3.5$ initial concn of $Fe + RH_2 = 2.182 \times 10^{-3} M$
 Filter Blue violet
 Curve II $pH \approx 3.5$, initial concn of $Fe + RH_2 = 8.728 \times 10^{-3} M$
 Filter Blue violet

corresponds to the composition of the violet compound to be $Fe : RH_2 = 1 : 1$ and from Fig-2 at $pH \approx 3.5$ with two different but equimolecular solutions, it is found that maximum value of the mixtures corresponds to the composition of the orange-red compound to be $Fe : RH_2 = 1 : 2$. Results are shown in Fig-1 and Fig-2.

B. Slope-ratio method:—For study of each complex two series of solutions were prepared in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. In one series, the concentration of the

$pH = 0.4$, filter - yellowish green

reagent was varied in presence of large excess of the Fe(III) which was kept constant. In the other, Fe(III) varied when the reagent was in large excess and kept constant. The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding standard hydrochloric acid and/or sodium acetate.

The optical densities of the solutions measured against water and the difference of the observed values and the calculated values if there be no reaction, were plotted against the concentration of the variable components. The ratio of the slopes of the two straight lines at $\text{pH} \approx 0.40$ in Fig-3 indicates the composition of the complex to be $\text{Fe} : \text{RH}_2 = 1 : 1$ and at $\text{pH} \approx 3.5$ in Fig-4 shows the composition of the complex to be $1 : 2$. Results are shown in Fig-3 and Fig-4. Spectral curves of the solutions containing Fe(III) and the reagent (RH_2) at different proportions and also at different pH values are shown in Fig-5.

Fig. 4.

$\text{pH} = 3.5$, filter - Blue violet.

Fig. 5.

Ferric nitrate and nitric acid could not be used as the reagent (RH_2) was oxidised in nitric acid medium.